

STUDIES ON THE MECHANISM OF AUTOXIDATION OF FATS.
PART II. OXIDATION OF METHYL OLEATE AND
METHYL LINOLEATE

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In course of autoxidation of fatty acids like oleic and linoleic and their methyl esters, oxygen achieves its effect by initiating its attack additively at the double bond of the unsaturated fatty acid molecules with the formation of cyclic peroxides. Oxidation is next found to proceed with the formation of hydroperoxides at a stage when initial cycloperoxidation of the unsaturated fatty acid molecules generates adequate energy to cause the disruption of an α -methylene hydrogen atom adjacent to the double bond.

In the previous paper (this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 230) the mechanism of autoxidation of unsaturated fatty acids by use of catalyst has been studied up to a primary stage of oxidation. The work outlined in this section has been conducted to study quantitatively the non-catalytic peroxidation and saturation of double bond relationship in a manner similar to that described in the previous paper using methyl oleate and linoleate as substrate. The oxidation was carried out at 37°, 60° and 110° with methyl oleate and at 37° only with the linoleate.

EXPERIMENTAL

The esters were prepared from the pure acids obtained as before by esterification with methyl alcohol by use of HCl gas as the catalyst. The esters were finally distilled under vacuum at 5 mm. to obtain pure products (b. p. 186° and 182.5° respectively). The autoxidation was carried out in 500 c.c. round-bottomed flasks by passing a slow stream of air from a compressor through the ester sufficient to keep the whole mass in a state of constant agitation. No mechanical shaking arrangement was provided. In experiments above the room temperature the flasks were immersed in an oil-bath, the temperature of which was regulated to maintain the esters at the desired temperature; usually a lower temperature (5°–8°) of the bath was required due to the exothermic nature of the reaction. At regular intervals a portion of the autoxidised sample was taken out and preserved in a refrigerator under CO₂ for subsequent analysis of peroxide, iodine and other values. The following tables represent the analytical figures obtained.

TABLE I

Oxidation of methyl oleate at 37°.

Days of blowing.	Peroxide values.	% Peroxide.*	Iodine value.	Drop in iodine value	
				Obs.	Calc.**
0	0	—	89.9	—	—
2	100	3.3	87.0	2.9	2.90
4	126	4.1	86.2	3.7	3.71
6	150	4.7	85.7	4.2	4.30
14	250	8.2	83.5	6.4	7.4
21	325	10.8	82.9	7.0	9.5
23	350	17.7	81.8	8.1	10.5
31	460	16.0	80.9	9.0	13.5
35	500	16.6	79.5	10.4	14.9
37	555	16.2	78.0	11.9	16.4
40	700	23.8	76.0	13.9	21.0
50	1000	33.8	72.6	17.3	26.5

TABLE II

Oxidation of methyl oleate at 60°.

Days of blowing.	Peroxide value.	% Peroxide.*	Iodine value.	Drop in iodine value	
				Obs.	Calc.**
0	0	—	89.9	—	—
3	400	13.3	78.6	11.3	11.9
7	810	26.7	77.4	12.5	23.8
14	1200	40.0	61.9	28.1	35.0
21	2710	90.0	36.5	53.4	60.9
28	1750	58.0	17.0	72.9	41.4

TABLE III

Oxidation of methyl oleate at 100°.

Hours of blowing.	Peroxide value.	% Peroxide.*	Iodine value.	Drop in iodine value	
				Obs.	Calc.**
4.5	687	22.6	89.5	20.4	20.8
24	1537	50.6	52.7	37.2	45.5
50	825	21.5	46.0	43.9	18.6
100	325	10.6	39.1	60.8	9.2

TABLE IV

Oxidation of methyl linoleate at 37°.

Hours of blowing.	Peroxide value.*	% Peroxide.*	Iodine value.	Drop in iodine value		% Diene conjugation.
				Obs.	Calc.**	
5	50	0.84	172.3	0.90	1.90	0.0
50	250	4.1	112.0	61.2	7.25	6.2
100	1975	22.5	85.7	87.5	40.80	18.7
150	2300	37.7	67.9	106.3	68.30	25.5
192	1310	21.5	67.8	106.4	38.90	15.2

These results are shown graphically in Figures 1 and 2.

* Calculated from full theor. p. v.

** Calculated on assumption that O_2 adds to double bond.

DISCUSSION

Methyl Oleate

The formation of peroxides and drop in iodine number at the early stages of oxidation clearly indicate that peroxide formation takes place entirely at the double bond. Thus, at 37° (Table I), up to 5-6% peroxidation of the molecules, the observed and calculated drops are identical. This effect is exceedingly marked at 100° where rapid peroxidation up to a very high figure (viz. 20-22%) is entirely through saturation of the double bonds. But it can be observed, as the oxidation proceeds further, that drop in iodine value observed is definitely less than that can be expected from the peroxidation at the double bond only, but at the same time the value appears to be greater than that demanded by exclusive formation of hydroperoxide. This relationship of an

FIG. 1
Oxidation of methyl oleate at 37° and at 60°.

observed fall, lower than that calculated from the peroxide formation, persists throughout the oxidation of methyl oleate at 37°, and as the temperature is raised to 60°, the same relationship is seen to hold good except that towards

the end of the oxidation the disappearance of the double bond is rapid and is in fact greater than that can be calculated from the percentage peroxidation data. There has also taken place simultaneous decomposition of peroxides (vide Table I) along with a rapid fall in iodine number, which is probably an indication that various decomposition and secondary reactions might be taking place. At 100° the oxidation is extremely rapid, about 25% peroxidation taking place in course of 5 hours, the peroxide formation and disappearance of double bond relationship still persist, though progressively weakened as oxidation proceeds, and there the decomposition of peroxides plays the predominant role.

Now at 37°, as the depression is less than that can be expected from the percentage peroxide formation data, once the initial stage of cent per cent saturation of double bonds is passed, one may assume that oxidation proceeds at some other point, and most possibly at the reactive methylene group, so that the rate of disappearance of double bonds by peroxidation is counterbalanced or depressed due to the formation of some compounds, definitely peroxidic in nature (because of the still increasing peroxidation observed), which also contains in tact double bonds, thus accounting for the partial fall in iodine value.

It evidently appears that hydroperoxidation of methyl oleate actually takes place, but Farmer's conclusions need certain modifications in the light of the above discussion and experimental results. He asserts that the primary product of peroxidation is a hydroperoxide. All the analytical data observed go to contradict this view and the opinion of the present author is that initial attack of oxygen is definitely at the ethenoid linkage as envisaged by early experimenters. As the rate of oxidation rapidly increases with time, the oxygen is able to utilise part of the energy liberated in such drastic oxidation in bringing about the disruption of one H atom of the active methylene group, ultimately resulting in the formation of compounds of hydroperoxidic nature. Moreover, it is very difficult to explain the formation of hydroperoxide at the initial stage because of the fact that separation of an α -methylene hydrogen atom requires 80 K. Cal. of energy, which must be supplied in some form or other, if hydroperoxidation starts at the beginning, and, hence the view expressed by the present author stands in a better position if at the same time it is remembered that the oxidation of methyl oleate is an exothermic reaction, and the heat evolved at the initial stage of cycloperoxidation might be sufficient to supply the energy requirement for subsequent hydroperoxidation of the methyl oleate.

The Oxidation of Methyl Linoleate

The conjugated diene unsaturation produced during the oxidation of methyl linoleate and recorded in Table IV above has been determined from the extinction coefficient of the absorption bands at 232 m μ (Brice *et al.*, *Oil & Soap*, 1945, 22,219). For this purpose solutions of the autoxidised esters

in absolute alcohol were employed. The ultraviolet spectra were obtained by means of a quartz spectrograph equipped with a Spekker photometer and a condensed tungsten-steel spark source of light. The maximum optical densities ($\log_{10} I_0/I$) at 2320 Å were determined by visual examination and interpolation of the match points on Kodak B20 plates. The photometer was carefully calibrated before each measurement by determination of blank match points, and the recording spectra were completed in each case within 15 minutes of admitting air to the specimen in order to prevent oxidation and polymerisation reactions.

FIG. 2
Oxidation of methyl linoleate.

The oxidation of methyl linoleate proceeds with a very short induction period, the peroxide values steadily rising to a certain maximum, followed by a rapid decomposition. The peroxidation is accompanied by development of diene conjugation, the amount of the latter increasing with nearly equal speed with that of peroxides. In the early stages of oxidation, the observed fall in iodine value is nearly an exact half of that can be expected from the theoretically calculated value of complete saturation of both the double bonds indicating, as in the case of catalytic oxidation of linoleic acid, that peroxidation of only one of the two double bonds takes place. The observed drop in iodine value soon, however, surpasses that calculated on the latter assumption. This can be explained by consideration of the progressive failure of the peroxide values

to indicate the absolute total quantity of peroxides produced in consequence of the secondary changes of the same, together with the presence of increasingly significant proportions of diene conjugation, which considerably vitiates the iodine value determination as carried out by Wij's method. It may be noticed that so long the saturation of one of the double bonds proceeds, there appears no significant amount of diene conjugation. From the data accumulated in this paper, it can be concluded that

(1) Oxidation of methyl linoleate starts by saturation of one of the double bonds only up to a certain initial stage of slow oxidation.

(2) Once this stage is passed, drastic oxidation results in simultaneous oxidation of the reactive methylene group of the acid molecule giving a hydroperoxide which afterwards rearranges with the formation of conjugated diene compounds, capable of further transformations such as polymerisation and decomposition. Any hypothesis of the initial formation of hydroperoxides, as postulated by Farmer, cannot be justified from the results obtained in course of the present investigation.

Development of Hydroxyl groups in the Oxidation of Methyl Oleate and Linoleate

The estimation of hydroxyl number of the oxidised samples described in Tables I, II and III has been carried out by the rapid method of Roberts and Schuette (*Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1932, 4, 287) by heating in sealed tubes with acetic anhydride and the results are shown in the following tables.

TABLE V

Development of OH groups in the oxidation of methyl oleate
(cf. Table II)

Experiments.	Acetyl No.	Peroxide value.
1. Methyl oleate oxidised at 100° for 4.5 hours	0.0	687
2. Methyl oleate " " 100° " 24 "	22.8	1537
3. Methyl oleate " " 100° " 50 "	33.9	828
4. Methyl oleate " " 100° " 100 "	23.75	325
5. Methyl oleate " " 37° " 50 days	38.0	—

TABLE VI

Development of OH groups in the oxidation of methyl linoleate
(cf. Table IV)

Experiments.	Acetyl No.	Peroxide value.
1. Methyl linoleate oxidised for 5 hrs. at 37°	0.02	50
2. Methyl linoleate " " 50 " " 37°	27.51	200
3. Methyl linoleate " " 100 " " 37°	51.51	1375
4. Methyl linoleate " " 150 " " 37°	88.08	2300
5. Methyl linoleate " " 181 " " 37°	77.75	1910

The results in Tables V and VI tend to show that development of hydroxyl groups during the oxidation of methyl oleate or linoleate takes place after an initial stage of full saturation of the double bonds by peroxidation alone, as practically very little hydroxyl groups have been introduced at the end of 4½ hours in case of methyl oleate at 100°, and 5 hours in case of methyl linoleate at 37° where it can be seen from the peroxide figures (Tables II and IV) that cent per cent peroxidation of the double bonds takes place. This indicates that hydroxyl compounds are derived possibly from the products of decomposition of the primary peroxides or more likely, the hydroperoxides which are formed subsequently. It may also be observed that with methyl linoleate the development of hydroxyl group increases *pri passu* up to a certain stage after which a fall in peroxide concentration is also accompanied by a decrease in the acetyl number.

The experimental evidences that have been obtained so far go to support the view that in course of the oxidation of oleic and linoleic acids and their methyl esters, the primary point of attack is the ethenoid bond of the unsaturated fatty acid molecules, entirely with the formation of peroxides. With the diethenoid linoleic acids, it has been established that during the initial stage of peroxidation only one of the two double bonds is saturated by oxygen in considerable speed. In the later stages of oxidation, however, both in the case of mono- and di-unsaturated acid, the oxygen further attacks the molecules possibly at the active methylene group with the formation of compounds, hydroperoxidic in nature. Since the separation of an α -methylene hydrogen atom requires about 80 K. Cal. of energy, any hypothesis of initial hydroperoxidation seems to be impossible. The present investigation suggests that during the early stages of oxidation a gradual activation of the fat molecules proceeds and active fat peroxides are being formed; accumulation of these and greatly accelerated rate of oxygen absorption may therefore result in facilitating the acquisition of a sufficient critical increment of energy by the fat molecules such that hydroperoxidation of the reactive methylene groups by separation of one α -methylene H atoms proceeds during the second phase of oxidation reactions. This investigation thus establishes the old peroxide theory and at the same time adds substantial support to the modern hydroperoxidation mechanism of autoxidation of fats, thus harmonising the discrepancies raised by different workers.

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